

Exploring the Efficacy of Play-Based Activities in Mitigating the Challenges of Dyscalculia among Students

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Abstract

Dyscalculia, a specific learning disability affecting mathematical abilities, poses significant challenges for students in their academic journey. This research investigates the impact of play-based activities as an intervention strategy for students with dyscalculia. By examining existing literature, empirical studies, and case reports, this research explores how play-based approaches can effectively address the cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects associated with dyscalculia. Through qualitative analysis, this study will examine the effectiveness of various play-based activities, such as games, manipulative, and interactive simulations, in enhancing mathematical skills, problem-solving abilities, self-confidence, and overall academic performance among students with dyscalculia. Additionally, this research will consider individual differences, educator training, and classroom implementation strategies to provide insights into best practices for incorporating play-based interventions in the educational context. The findings of this study aim to inform educators, special education professionals, and policymakers about the potential of play-based approaches in supporting students with dyscalculia and promoting inclusive and effective mathematics education.

Keywords: Dyscalculia, Play-based Activities, Specific Learning Disability.

Introduction

Specific Learning Disability

"Specific Learning Disabilities as a heterogeneous group of conditions wherein there is a deficit in processing language, spoken or written, that may manifest itself as a difficulty to comprehend, speak, read, write, spell, or to do mathematical calculations and includes such conditions as perceptual disabilities, dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia, dyspraxia, and developmental aphasia." (RPWD2016)

Learning disability is referred to as a hidden disability as children with learning disabilities do not look disabled and their difficulties are not obvious. Learning difficulties in children, thus, suffer from low self-esteem, confidence, and motivation as a result of being misinterpreted and accused of not listening, being lazy, or being clumsy. Therefore, when a child exhibits an educationally significant disparity between his or her predicted intellectual capacity and actual school performance that cannot be explained in terms of intellectual potential, we can consider the child to be suffering from a learning disability. These kids could struggle with speaking, listening, reading, understanding, spelling, doing math problems, writing, and concepts. Intelligence in children with learning disabilities can range from normal to above average.

A neuro developmental disorder, learning disability is not caused by problems with hearing or vision, socioeconomic status, cultural or linguistic disparities, low motivation, or inadequate or inadequate training.

The brain's capacity to perceive and interpret spoken and nonverbal information is influenced by a complex interplay of biologically derived genetic, epigenetic, and environmental factors effectively and efficiently. Beyond the common misconception that learning disabilities are limited to letter problems or reading difficulties. Both in terms of the meanings they affect and the intensity of the influence felt, they are very different. The right accommodations are determined by the person's unique difficult situations and strengths. (Chand.S 2021)

Dyscalculia

Dyscalculia refers to a 'pattern of difficulties characterized by problems with processing numerical information, learning arithmetic facts, and performing accurate or fluent calculation' (APA 2013, p. 67) Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders [DSM-5]

Dyscalculia is difficulty in learning or comprehending arithmetic such as difficulty in understanding numbers, learning how to manipulate numbers, and learning math facts. It is generally seen as a specific developmental disorder like dyslexia. Dyscalculia is a mathematical learning disorder where mathematical ability is far below expected for a person's age, intelligence, and education. Dyscalculia is a broad term that includes many kinds of difficulties in learning mathematics. Children with Dyscalculia tend to be of normal intelligence. Although in the absence of concomitant reading issues, their problems with math will be noted. Dyscalculia excel at performing extremely complex arithmetic problems but still require assistance with the fundamentals. Arithmetic learning disorders, often known as developmental dyscalculia, refer to specific and notable challenges with learning mathematical concepts. It is noteworthy that dyscalculia is not a monolithic concept, and that individual differences in the cognitive profiles associated with it can be substantial (Kaufmann and Nuerk 2005; Wilson and Dehaene 2007).

Math challenges are collectively referred to as dyscalculia. Pupils suffering from dyscalculia may struggle with visual-spatial concepts, which are important in geometry and pattern building, as well as comprehending the meaning of numbers, recalling arithmetic facts, and following methods to solve math problems. Language processing issues may be linked to dyscalculia, leading to challenges in acquiring the mathematical vocabulary required to comprehend mathematical ideas and work through more challenging tasks.

Challenges Faced by Children with Dyscalculia

- **Social Skills:** If a youngster consistently performs poorly in math class, they may come to believe that failure in other subjects is unavoidable. A child's willingness to participate in after-school activities or establish new acquaintances may be impacted by low self-esteem. The youngster may also steer clear of sports and games that require math or keeping score.
- **Orientation:** Toddler may struggle to distinguish between left and right. He can find it difficult to read maps or follow instructions to go to locations. Some kids who struggle with math struggle to see things. The youngster could find it difficult to picture how a structure or other three-dimensional item would appear from a different perspective. They will struggle to know where to go as a result. Driving will become problematic as a result of this as people age.
- **Physical Coordination:** The way the brain and eyes cooperate can be impacted by dyscalculia. As a result, a kid could struggle to determine how far apart objects are. The kid could appear more awkward than other children of the same age.
- **Money Management:** It can be challenging for someone with dyscalculia to estimate expenses, balance a checkbook, and follow a budget. It may also complicate tip calculation and precise change counting.
- **Time Management:** A youngster with dyscalculia may find it difficult to measure quantities, especially time. The child can find it difficult to gauge the length of a minute or to keep track of the passing of time. It may be challenging to follow a timetable as a result.(UNESCO MGIEP)

Causes of Dyscalculia

The brain regions and mathematical processes that are malfunctioning lead to dyscalculia. Dyscalculia affects 6% of students, around the same percentage as dyslexics (LDAM, 2005). The brain's parietal lobe

contains the intraparietal sulcus, or IPS (intraparietal sulcus), which is where numerical magnitude is processed, according to studies. According to data, children who are dyscalculic have a breakdown in the relationship between the IPS's activity and numerical distance (Ansari, 2008). Children who struggle with math have an incomplete or unconnected IPS.

Effect of Play-Based Activities for Dyscalculia-

Play-based activities can have a significant and varied impact on dyscalculia. Every level of the educational process, starting with pre-school education, should incorporate plays, and teachers should encourage and establish a supportive educational atmosphere for the child (Aksoy, 2014; Koçyiğitet et al., 2007). For kids, play is a serious endeavour. Plays help kids learn and explore the world (Güneş, 2015). In the realm of education, the practice of "learning with plays" is gradually becoming more popular as plays are an effective and permanent form of instruction (Cohrsen et al., 2013; Cutter-Mackenzie & Edwards, 2013; Nolan & Paatsch, 2018; Pyle & Danniels, 2017; Robertson et al., 2018; Sumsion et al., 2014). The goal of the play-based learning strategy is to get kids involved in the educational process and learn while having fun. It helps kids develop abilities including problem-solving, cognitive activities, attention, and interest. Children's abilities including problem-solving, cognitive exercises, attention to detail, and engagement in activities are all enhanced by it (Güneş, 2015). It also teaches how to use the trial-and-error method to determine the best course of action after making mistakes. Plays are another useful tool for engaging mathematicians.

The active learning approach known as "teaching through play" (Şahin, 2005) has found its way into mathematics education as it has in many other subjects (Özgenç, 2010). This approach works particularly well for removing biases and learning and retaining mathematical concepts (Altunay, 2004). (Pesen, 2003). Techniques such as employing imaginative materials and play-based exercises, conducting individual or group research, illustrating the connections between mathematics and everyday life, and stressing the concepts and activities are advised for preventing or lessening children's math anxiety.

(Alkan & Altun, 1998; Bekdemir et al., 2004; Dodd, 1992; Ramani & Scalise, 2018; Scalise et al., 2017).

Play-Based Activities

When working with individuals who have dyscalculia, it's important to engage them in activities that help build number sense, strengthen mathematical concepts, and promote positive associations with math. Here are some play-based activities tailored for individuals with dyscalculia:

- **Number Bingo:** Create bingo cards with numbers or simple math problems that the individual can solve. Make sure the problems are within their ability range. This game helps reinforce number recognition and basic arithmetic skills in a fun way.
- **Math Board Games:** There are many board games available that incorporate math skills, such as Monopoly, or even custom-made math board games. These games provide opportunities for practicing counting, addition, subtraction, and strategy.
- **Math Storytelling:** Use storytelling to introduce math concepts. Create stories or scenarios where the individual must use math to solve problems or make decisions. This approach can make math more engaging and relatable.
- **Math Manipulatives:** Utilize physical objects like blocks, counters, or beads to represent numbers and math operations. Hands-on activities with manipulatives can help individuals with dyscalculia better understand abstract mathematical concepts.
- **Cooking and Baking:** Involve the individual in cooking or baking activities that require measurements and calculations. For example, they can measure ingredients, adjust recipes, or divide portions. This practical application of math can make it more meaningful and enjoyable.
- **Outdoor Math Scavenger Hunt:** Create a scavenger hunt where the individual has to find and solve math-related clues or problems outdoors. This activity combines physical movement with math practice, making it engaging and interactive.

- **Math Art:** Integrate math with art activities. For instance, create geometric shapes using colored paper or use symmetry to design patterns. This allows the individual to explore mathematical concepts creatively.
- **Math Puzzles and Riddles:** Provide puzzles, brain teasers, or riddles that involve math concepts. Encourage the individual to solve them using logical thinking and problem-solving skills. This can help develop mathematical reasoning abilities.

Play-based activities offer a promising approach to alleviating math anxiety and promoting a positive attitude toward mathematics in students with dyscalculia. By creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment and incorporating hands-on, interactive activities into math instruction, special education teachers can help students overcome their fear of math and develop the confidence and skills needed to succeed in mathematics.

This study looks into how well play-based interventions work to help primary school kids with dyscalculia overcome their difficulties. One particular type of learning disability that affects a large number of people and has a major influence on arithmetic ability is dyscalculia. It's commonly called "dyslexia with numbers," a term that emphasizes how much dyslexia and dyscalculia overlap in terms of their effects and backup.

Review of Literature

(**Altundağ.C 2023**) studied the Design of Educational and Digital Games for Students with Dyscalculia to Transfer Mathematics to Their Daily Lives strives to develop instructional and online games that support dyscalculic students in applying mathematical ideas to their daily lives. According to the research, teaching children with dyscalculia to apply math to real-world scenarios can improve their learning and cognitive flexibility. Through the use of digital teaching resources and games that mimic real-world settings, students can investigate and comprehend mathematical ideas in a variety of contexts and ways. This method makes learning more interesting and hands-on, allowing students to apply their mathematical understanding to real-world situations.

(**Francisco.T 2022**) the study looked into how game-based design exercises affected students' algebra proficiency levels, with a particular emphasis on improving computational abilities for factoring quadratic equations. The study employed a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control-group design, in which one group participated in an online game named "Quadratic Rush" and the other group was subjected to conventional teaching techniques. Both the control and experimental groups' post-test results exceeded their pre-test results, demonstrating a performance improvement. When compared to students who participated in traditional activities, students who participated in the game-based activity scored higher, indicating that the "Quadratic Rush" game is a useful tool for enhancing computational skills. According to the study, educators could use games to help students understand other mathematical ideas and create original game prototypes that cater to the requirements and interests of their students.

(**Ramirez.E Jamis.M 2022**) This study suggests a mobile game-based learning system for mathematics at WordLab School Inc. that uses role-playing games, or RPGs for short, to assist fourth-grade kids with dyscalculia and math learning difficulties. Math learning disabilities are similar to dyscalculia but on a smaller scale. Dyscalculia is a term used to describe having trouble understanding mathematics on many levels, including weakness in understanding the meaning of numbers and difficulty applying mathematical principles to solve problems. There are many different ways to study in the classroom these days, and one of them is termed "gamified learning," in which students can enhance their education and make it more interesting for themselves by playing games. With the use of this mobile game-based learning approach, teachers may keep an eye on their student's progress in math classes by using the online application that monitors the game while the students play and study according to their curriculum. Additionally, while professors are keeping an eye on their progress, students can play multiplayer games during quiz time in their classroom. Using the web application, teachers can create and edit questions for their pupils.

(**Panday.S Agarwal.S 2014**) discovered that playing video games helps pupils develop their cognitive, problem-solving, and spatial skills while also incorporating positive learning principles. When a child

with special educational needs (SEN) has a history of failing school, they can be especially helpful. The goal of the video game "Space Adventure: Defend the Planet!" is to help deaf and hearing youngsters with special education needs become more proficient in math. To rebuild a space station, players must apply basic mathematical and spatial principles. The purpose of the study was to evaluate students' involvement with the video game and their improvement in mathematical achievement. The participants' performance in mathematics improved by 4% to 19%, according to the data.

(Single.V at. 2020) studies that children with dyscalculia may not benefit from traditional learning methods since they frequently lose interest. Gamification, or learning through games, is a useful strategy for supporting dyscalculia students and increasing motivation. Since gamification is not frequently acknowledged as a learning tool, it is critical to be aware of its potential advantages. Gamification's primary goal is to give dyscalculia pupils access to technology. Students with dyscalculia can learn more effectively while having a more entertaining and engaging experience when game components are included in the curriculum.

(Carrión.P 2018) studied Several software technologies and the agile XP approach that have been used to create an instructional game for kids with dyscalculia. Initial and primary school institutions have submitted the game for validation. The game assists in addressing challenges related to switching between arithmetic operations, comprehending magnitude differences, recalling computation stages, identifying and utilizing arithmetic symbols, and replicating or copying numbers and figures. The game's creation was made easier by the XP approach, which offered iterative versions for user feedback. The game has been demonstrated to be a useful treatment tool for children with dyscalculia and is based on non-technological didactic tools that are frequently utilized for this disorder.

(Drigas.A & Pappas.M 2015) conducted a study on educational video games offering an enjoyable approach to teaching basic concepts and enhancing cognitive abilities, there has been a noticeable increase in interest in mathematics education. Through improving their experiences, video games can improve pupils' motivation and learning progress. Researchers are becoming more and more interested in creating new educational video games and using them to teach mathematics. However, creating an instructional game that kids will find entertaining and appealing is a difficult task. Positive findings have been found when the impact of playing video games on executive control, memory, and attention has been studied. Playing video games while teaching arithmetic can help kids become more proficient in the subject and develop positive attitudes toward it.

(Aljojo.N 2018) This study presents the design and development of a game-based learning application aimed at enhancing young children's mathematics proficiency. Students studying addition and subtraction in elementary school are the application's intended audience. There are chances for improved learning environments with the use of technology, which can replace the antiquated traditional learning method in schools. Through the use of pleasure and education in a math learning game, this initiative seeks to enhance the arithmetic abilities of young children, ages 6 to 8 The influence of the Mathematics Game-Based Learning Application was assessed using an experimental study. Overall, the findings point to an improvement in the learning process. Children can strengthen their hand-eye coordination, linguistic abilities, and attention to detail with the use of educational technology.

Findings

The literature review underscores the potential of play-based activities in addressing the challenges of dyscalculia among students. By engaging students in hands-on, interactive experiences, play-based interventions offer effective strategies for promoting mathematical learning and overcoming barriers to success in mathematics. However, further research is needed to explore the long-term effects and optimal implementation strategies of play-based approaches for dyscalculia across different age groups and educational settings. Nonetheless, the findings review underscores the importance of incorporating play-based activities as a valuable component of comprehensive intervention efforts for students with dyscalculia. By incorporating play-based activities into the classroom environment, special education teachers can create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where students with dyscalculia

feel empowered to overcome their fear of math and develop a positive attitude toward mathematical learning.

Conclusion

The exploration into the efficacy of play-based activities in mitigating the challenges of dyscalculia among students highlights promising avenues for intervention and support. Through a thorough examination of existing literature, empirical studies, and case reports, several key insights have emerged. Play-based activities offer a dynamic and engaging approach to addressing the cognitive, affective, and behavioral difficulties associated with dyscalculia. By incorporating elements of play into mathematical learning experiences, educators can create inclusive and supportive environments that cater to the diverse needs of students with dyscalculia.

Overall, the evidence suggests that play-based activities hold great promise as a valuable tool for supporting students with dyscalculia and promoting their mathematical success. As such, it is essential for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to recognize the importance of play in mathematics education and to advocate for the integration of play-based interventions in educational settings. By leveraging the power of play, we can create inclusive and effective learning environments that empower all students to thrive academically and socially, regardless of their mathematical abilities.

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